

Potentiometric Study of Oxidation of Coordinated Malonic Acid

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Oxidation of monomalonatodiaquo copper (II) has been studied under different conditions. In course of the reaction KMnO_4 is reduced to Mn(II) and malonate is oxidised to CO_2 . Perhaps Cu(II) in the complexed state plays an important role in the redox process.

SO far several authors¹⁻⁵ have investigated the oxidation of uncoordinated malonic acid. But the oxidation of coordinated malonic acid has been left untouched. This led us to study the oxidation of coordinated malonic acid (in the form of monomalonate diaquo copper(II)).

Experimental

The stages of the oxidation were followed potentiometrically⁶ using bright platinum electrode. The concentrations were so chosen that 10ml malonic acid (both coordinated and uncoordinated) solution required 16ml oxidant solution for complete oxidation to CO_2 stage. The experimental results are tabulated below.

TABLE 1

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=0.5\text{ M}$

Cell : 10 ml M/50 Malonic acid solution

Oxidant : M/50 KMnO_4 solution.

Temp. in °C Time in hrs	Position of inflexion in ml.	Nature of inflexions.
Room Temp.	1.85	Vague
48	14.00	Sharp
85°	1.85	Vague
4	15.30	Very sharp
85°	1.85	Vague
20	15.45	Very sharp

TABLE 2

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=1.0\text{ M}$

Cell : 10 ml M/50 Malonic acid solution

Oxidant : M/50 KMnO_4 solution.

Temp. in °C Time in hrs	Position of inflexion in ml.	Nature of inflexions
Room Temp.	1.85	Vague
24	13.50	Sharp
85°	1.85	Vague
4	15.00	Sharp
85°	12.00	Vague
20	15.35	Very sharp.

TABLE 3

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=4.0\text{ M}$

Cell : 10 ml M/50 Malonic acid solution

Oxidant : M/50 KMnO_4 solution.

Temp. in °C Time in hrs.	Position of inflexions in ml.	Nature of inflexions.
Room Temp.	1.85	Vague
48	13.50	Sharp
85°		
4	15.40	Very sharp.

TABLE 4

[H₂SO₄]=2.0 M

Cell : 10 ml M/50 Cu(II) monomalonate complex.

Oxidant : M/50 KMnO₄ solution.

Temp. in °C Time in hrs.	Position of inflexions in ml.	Nature of inflexions.
Room Temp.	1.90	Vague
14	12.40	Sharp
85°	2.15	Vague
2	13.25	Sharp
85°		
4	15.75	Very sharp.

Discussion

The stoichiometry for the reaction between Cu(II) malonate complex and permanganate can be represented by the overall equation

The first step is probably acid hydrolysis of Cu(II) malonate complex to form free malonic acid

Other probable steps are

Malonic acid formed in reaction step (2), is probably oxidised⁴ by Mn(III) or Cu(III).

To explain the requirement of a rapid reaction between Cu(II) malonate complex and acid KMnO₄, the following scheme may be postulated

The reaction step (7) involves oxidation of Cu(II) to Cu(III) while remaining bound to the complex⁷.

In this step the electron transfer takes place in the coordinated stage, as a result of which the radical ion $\cdot\text{OOC} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{COO}^-$ is formed. This radical ion may further be stabilised by protonation and dimerisation forming thereby peroxydimalonate, corresponding to the first vague inflexion (Table-4) or be oxidised to give various intermediate species and finally CO₂ and H₂O. Cu(II) has secondary catalytic effect, the primary catalyst is Mn(II). Similar⁸ effect has been found for Ru(III)/Ru(IV) in the system containing malonic acid, potassium bromate and Ce(III)/Ce(IV).

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